

Proceedings of the 1st GOBLIN Workshop on Knowledge Graph Technologies

Leipzig, Germany — June 12, 2025

Edited by: Milan Dojchinovski and Blerina Spahiu

Organised upon work from the CA23147 COST Action
*GOBLIN: Global Network on Large-Scale, Cross-domain and Multilingual
Open Knowledge Graphs*

Introduction

Knowledge Graphs are transforming the way we model, integrate, and analyze complex data, with applications spanning finance, health, robotics, and other domains, as well as in technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, data science, and automation. To advance this growing field, the 1st GOBLIN Workshop on Knowledge Graph Technologies was organized under the umbrella of the GOBLIN COST Action (<https://www.cost.eu/actions/CA23147/>). The Action aims to increase and enhance publicly available open knowledge in Europe and beyond by providing a large-scale, high-quality, cross-domain, and multilingual knowledge graph technology that is free to use, reuse, and redistribute.

The workshop, held in Leipzig, Germany, on June 12, 2025, brought together researchers, practitioners, and stakeholders to discuss cutting-edge developments in knowledge graph technologies, applications, and open challenges. It served as a platform for exchanging insights and fostering collaboration between academia and industry in the rapidly evolving knowledge graph ecosystem.

Contributions spanned innovations in engineering, managing, and utilizing knowledge graphs across diverse domains. Topics included methods, tools, applications, datasets, benchmarks, and frameworks, as well as other relevant advances that push the boundaries of current knowledge graph research and practice. By highlighting both opportunities and challenges, the workshop encouraged participants to collectively advance the state of the art in this field.

This booklet provides an overview of the accepted papers presented at the workshop, together with their links to Zenodo DOIs, offering a valuable resource for further exploration and research.

Accepted Papers

- 1. A Multi-Agent System for Semantic Mapping of Relational Data to Knowledge Graphs**
Milena Trajanoska, Riste Stojanov and Dimitar Trajanov
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16911414
- 2. A Visual Notation for Web-Based Ontology Modeling**
Julija Ovcinnikova and Karlis Cerans
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16911656
- 3. Bridging the Gap Between Natural Language and Semantic Web: A Text-to-SPARQL System**
Dimitar Pavlovski and Riste Stojanov
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16912011
- 4. An Event-centered Knowledge Graph for Bulgaria**
Kiril Simov, Nikolay Paev and Petya Osenova
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16912113
- 5. AI Agent-Driven Framework for Automated Product Knowledge Graph Construction in E-Commerce**
Dimitar Peshevski, Riste Stojanov and Dimitar Trajanov
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16912163
- 6. Towards Generating Synthetic EHR Knowledge Graphs — a Probabilistic Approach**
Milos Jovanovik, Eva Milenkova, Maxime Jakubowski and Katja Hose
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16912250
- 7. Prompting or Fine-tuning? Evaluating Relation Classification in Portuguese for Knowledge Graph Construction**
Tomás Pinto, Bruno Ferreira, Catarina Silva and Hugo Gonçalo Oliveira
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16912342
- 8. LLM-Powered Knowledge Graphs vs Topic Modelling for Sustainable Development Analytics**
Buket Fildisi, Edlira Vakaj, Amna Dridi and Atif Azad
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16912396
- 9. From LLM Generation to Knowledge Representation: Creating and Structuring the GeminiKnowledge-sr QA Dataset for Serbian**
Ranka Stankovic, Nikola Jankovic, Jovana Radenovic and Milica Ikonc Nestic
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16912469

10. **The CK25 Corporate Knowledge Reference Dataset for Benchmarking Text 2 SPARQL Question Answering Approaches**
Sebastian Tramp and René Pietzsch
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16912605
11. **Digitizing and Structuring Early Marine Biodiversity Records: A GraphRAG-Based Methodology**
Gustavo Nuñez, Marcos Zárate, Darío Ceballos and Pablo Fillottrani
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16912811
12. **Smart Learning Applications with the combination of the Open Research Knowledge Graph and Teaching Knowledge Graphs**
Eleni Ilkou and Sören Auer
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16912917
13. **Towards personal data store-based retrieval augmented generation in mobile computing**
Zachary Grider and Alexander Nelson
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16913027
14. **Can Personal KG-based RAG Empower Patients?**
Mariana Dias and Carla Teixeira Lopes
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16913140

Citation

If you wish to cite the proceedings as a whole, please use the following reference:

Proceedings of the 1st GOBLIN Workshop on Knowledge Graph Technologies (Leipzig, Germany, June 12, 2025). Edited by Milan Dojchinovski and Blerina Spahiu. Published in the GOBLIN COST Action Zenodo community. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.16913321](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16913321)

Acknowledgment

This workshop was organized upon work from the GOBLIN COST Action: CA23147 – Global Network on Large-Scale, Cross-domain and Multilingual Open Knowledge Graphs (CA23147), supported by COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology). <https://www.cost.eu>